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Experimental and theoretical insights into the oxodiperoxomolybdenum-catalysed sulphide oxidation using hydrogen peroxide in ionic liquids[†]

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The oxidation of organic sulphides with aqueous hydrogen peroxide in ionic liquids (ILs) and catalysed by oxodiperoxomolybdenum complexes was investigated. The selective formation of several sulfones was achieved by using the 1:3 ratio of sulphide:H₂O₂ in [C₄mim][PF₆] (C₄mim = 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium) in a reaction catalysed by [Mo(O)(O₂)₂(H₂O)_n] complex. Conversely, sulfoxides were produced with good selectivities by using a 1:1 ratio in the same solvent in a 1h reaction with [Mo(O)(O₂)₂(Mepz)₂] (Mepz = methylpyrazol). The use of [C₄mim][PF₆] as solvent was advantageous for two reasons: i) the improved performance of the H₂O₂/IL combination; ii) recycling of the catalyst/IL mixture without a significant diminution of conversion or selectivity. A DFT analysis using the [Mo(O)(O₂)₂(L)] catalysts (L = Mepz, **a**; 3,5-dimethylpyrazol, dmpz, **b**; and H₂O, **c**) indicated that a Sharpless-type outer-sphere mechanism is more probable than a Thiel-type one. The highest barrier of the catalytic profile was the oxo-transfer step, in which the nucleophilic attack of sulphide into the peroxide ligand occurred with formation of dioxoperoxo species. In order to yield the sulfoxide and the starting catalyst, the oxidation of the resulting dioxoperoxo species with H₂O₂ was found to be the most favourable pathway. Subsequently, the sulfoxide to sulfone oxidation was produced through a similar mechanism involving the [Mo(O)(O₂)₂(L)] catalyst. The comparable energies found for both the successive two oxo-transfer steps were in agreement with the experimental formation of sulfone in both the reaction with an excess of oxidant and the stoichiometric one in the absence of oxidant. In the latter case, diphenylsulfone was isolated as the major product in the 1:1 combination of diphenylsulphide and [Mo(O)(O₂)₂(Mepz)₂] in the ionic liquid [C₄mim][PF₆]. Also, the compounds [HMepz]₄[Mo₈O₂₆(Mepz)₂]·2H₂O, **1**, [Hdmpz]₄[Mo₈O₂₆(dmpz)₂]·2dmpz, **2**, and [Hpz]₄[Mo₈O₂₂(O₂)₄(pz)₂]·3H₂O, **3**, were obtained by treating in water, stoichiometrically, dimethylsulfoxide and the corresponding [Mo(O)(O₂)₂(L)₂] complex (L = Mepz; 3,5-dimethylpyrazole, dmpz; pyrazol, pz). The crystal structures of octanuclear compounds **1-3** was an indirect proof of the formation of the theoretically proposed intermediates.

Introduction

Oxidation of organic sulphides is a useful and financially beneficial strategy for organic synthesis, since sulfoxides and sulfones are key intermediates toward chemically and

biologically added value compounds.^{1,2,3,4} This transformation is generally achieved by using stoichiometric amounts of organic and inorganic reagents,⁵ most of which are unsuitable in large-scale syntheses, because they may generate toxic wastes. Indeed, the usage of environmentally-benign oxidants and low impact solvents in catalysis is a priority of modern green chemistry.⁶ Additionally, the desulfurization of fuels and wastes by oxidation reactions has acquired major environmental interest.⁷

Several oxidants are available to perform the transformation of sulphides into sulfoxides and sulfones, but for sustainable economic and environmental strategies the choice of greener reactants is imposed.⁸ Amongst the latter, aqueous hydrogen peroxide has environmentally-benign characteristics, since it only produces harmless water as a by-product. Moreover, it is safe for storage and handling and it is cheap, readily available and has a highly-efficient oxygen content. For these reasons, there has been an acceleration in the development of valuable procedures for the oxidation of sulphides with aqueous hydrogen peroxide⁹ in combination with a variety of transition metal compounds as catalysts, in particular, d⁰ transition metal compounds of titanium,¹⁰ vanadium,¹¹ molybdenum,^{12,13} tungsten^{8c,13c,14} and rhenium.¹⁵ Depending on the selectivity of the catalyst and the method of choice, sulfoxide and sulfone are produced in different ratios.

During the last few years interest in ionic liquids (ILs) as alternatives to common organic solvents has markedly grown.¹⁶ The ILs can solubilise many inorganic compounds, whilst being immiscible with many common extraction solvents. This means that a catalyst will often be immobilised in the ionic liquid while products are separated by extraction, allowing the catalyst to be recycled.¹⁷ Plenty of examples of the catalytic oxidation of organic compounds in IL solvents have been reported,¹⁸ including numerous examples of metal-catalysed sulphide oxidations.^{10a,b,12b,13a,14a,15a,19} Recently, Kühn and co-workers have achieved, in the ionic liquid [C₄mim][BF₄] (C₄mim = 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium), a highly selective and efficient oxidation of sulphides into sulfoxides without a catalyst but employing aqueous hydrogen peroxide as an oxidant.²⁰

On these bases, green sulfoxidation, as a topic of extraordinary importance, requires clear understanding of the associated reaction mechanisms to improve efficiency. Even though computational chemistry is an optimal tool to study pathways, only a limited number of theoretical articles have appeared on the metal-free²¹ and metal-catalysed²² oxidation of sulphides. With relation to the latter, the catalytic epoxidation of olefins has comparatively received much wider theoretical attention.²³ Some of the few DFT studies on sulfoxidation

over molybdenum-catalysed systems have been carried out by Sensato²⁴ and Calhorda,²⁵ by focusing on oxodiperoxo and dioxocyclopentadienyl complexes, respectively.

Following our recent research on catalysed oxidations in non-conventional media,²⁶ and the acquired knowledge on oxodiperoxomolibdenum-catalysed olefin epoxidation in ionic liquids,^{27,28} we decided to explore the oxodiperoxomolibdenum-catalysed sulphide oxidation using hydrogen peroxide in the [C₄mim][PF₆] medium (Scheme 1). Oxo-molybdenum(VI) precursors are well-known as catalysts for sulphide oxidations,¹² and in particular oxodiperoxomolibdenum(VI) complexes have been proven as active catalysts when using hydrogen peroxide as an oxidant.^{13,29} This type of processes have been theoretically investigated by Sensato and co-workers,²⁴ who analyzed the first steps of the Me₂S oxidation over the complex [Mo(O)(O₂)₂(OPH₃)]. In order to justify some of our experimental observations, we also adopted a DFT approach,³⁰ exploring the entire catalytic cycle for the sulfoxidation of the Me₂S or MePhS substrate with hydrogen peroxide upon the catalysts [Mo(O)(O₂)₂(L)] (L = methylpyrazole, Mepz; 3,5-dimethylpyrazole, dmpz; or water). Additionally, the stoichiometric reaction of [Mo(O)(O₂)₂(L)₂] complex and Me₂S in absence of H₂O₂ oxidant was investigated.

Scheme 1

Results and discussion

Influence of the solvent, oxidant, and catalyst in sulfoxidation

It is generally accepted that the oxidation of sulphides containing electron-donating substituents lead to better yields than other sulphides containing electron-withdrawing or less electron-donating groups. Indeed, a larger nucleophilicity at the sulphur atom favour the sulphide reactivity. Therefore, diphenylsulphide was selected as the appropriate substrate for preliminary investigations, because it is less prone to sulfoxidation than other employed dialkyl- or alkylaryl- sulphides (e.g., the thioanisole). To begin with, the readily available molybdenum(VI) trioxide, MoO₃, was chosen as the precursor of the

oxodiperoxomolibdenum catalyst. Reactions were carried out on a 1 mmol scale employing a solution of MoO₃ (2.5 % mmol) in aqueous hydrogen peroxide, prepared as described elsewhere.^{27c} For the purpose of simplicity, the solution is referred to in this work as [Mo(O)(O₂)₂(H₂O)_n]. Several common solvents were tested in order to make comparisons with the imidazolium-based ionic liquid. Table 1 reports selected results from the reactions carried out in a micro-reactor (2 ml of solvent) with a 1:3:0.025 ratio of [diphenylsulphide:oxidant:catalyst].

Sulphide oxidation was found to be strongly dependent on the solvent and the oxidant used and the only solvent/oxidant efficient combination appeared to be the ionic liquid/H₂O₂. The conventional solvents H₂O, Cl₃CH and DMSO (entries 1–3 of Table 1) only afforded low yields of the oxidised product after 18 h of reaction at 20 °C, possibly due to an insufficient solubility of the various reaction components. For instance, the molybdenum catalyst and H₂O₂ are insoluble in Cl₃CH, whilst diphenylsulphide is insoluble in water. Conversely, in the ionic liquid [C₄mim][PF₆], complete reaction occurred already after 1h (compares entries 4 and 5 in Table 1). The reaction was totally selective for the sulfone product, since no sulfoxide was observed. Since the temperature affects the yields (at 0 °C the reaction is still incomplete after 1 h as shown by the entry 6 in Table 1), it was decided to perform all the reactions at 20 °C with a reaction time of 1h.

Different imidazolium-based ionic liquids also favoured high yields of the sulfone product (entries 7-9, Table 1) under the given reaction conditions. Oxidation clearly proceeded via a metal-catalysed mechanism, since no conversion was observed after 1 h at 20 °C in the absence of a Mo complex (entry 10, Table 1). Consider that the reaction time for the diphenylsulphide oxidation with hydrogen peroxide in the absence of a metal catalyst and in [C₄mim][BF₄] is 24 h²⁰, or even 32 h⁹ in the absence of an organic solvent. For further comparisons, *tert*-butyl hydroperoxide (TBHP) and lithium perchlorate were used as oxidants under the given conditions. The catalytic activity decreased notably for TBHP (entry 11, Table 1), although the reaction selectively afforded sulfoxide. Conversely, in the case of the perchlorate salt, its insolubility prevents the reaction (entry 12, Table 1).

Pyrazole derivatives have been used as ligands of oxobisperoxomolybdenum complexes in order to increase the catalytic feature in oxidation catalysis.^{13f,31} For instance, [Mo(O)(O₂)₂(Mepz)₂] (Mepz = 3-methylpyrazole) has been reported by us as a more efficient catalyst than [Mo(O)(O₂)₂(H₂O)_n] in epoxidation reactions in [C₄mim][PF₆].²⁸ As such, we have also investigated the activity of the molybdenum complex [Mo(O)(O₂)₂(Mepz)₂] as catalyst of our selected test reaction in [C₄mim][PF₆] (entry 13, Table 1). Conversion and

selectivity to the sulfone indicated that this reaction also runs to completion, impeding a fair comparison of the activity of systems employing $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{Mepz})_2]$ or $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n]$ as catalyst. However, a further study was conducted using a lower catalyst/substrate ratio. Under these conditions, differences in the maximum achievable yields for the systems tested should become apparent. When the reaction was carried out employing only 0.25 % Mo complex, conversions of sulphide using $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n]$ (entry 14, Table 1) or $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{Mepz})_2]$ (entry 15, Table 1) were found to be similar; however, different ratios of sulfoxide/sulfone were clearly observed, indicating that the presence of a pyrazole ligand in the Mo catalyst could reduce over-oxidation of the sulfoxide to the sulfone. Therefore, in order to obtain complete oxidation to sulfone, the complex $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n]$ appears to be the optimal Mo catalyst. Conversely, the complex $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{Mepz})_2]$ as catalyst should be suitable when sulfoxide is the target product. The diminution of the Lewis acidity of the molybdenum centre by Mepz coordination decreases the electrophilicity of the peroxide ligand, making sulfoxide oxidation more difficult. This fact has been confirmed by the computation of higher barriers for the catalyst with Mepz in comparison with those containing a H_2O ligand (see below).

Influence of the substrate/oxidant ratio on Mo-catalysed sulfoxidation

As shown in Fig. 1, different proportions of sulfoxide and sulfone were produced depending on the substrate to oxidant ratio used. The reactions were studied under the following reaction conditions: micro-reactor, 2 ml of $[\text{C}_4\text{mim}][\text{PF}_6]$, using $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n]$ as catalyst and hydrogen peroxide as oxidant, with a 1:0.025 ratio of [diphenylsulphide:catalyst], maintained at 20 °C for 18 h. The reaction led selectively to sulfone when a substrate to oxidant ratio of 1:3 was applied. Increasing the ratio of substrate to oxidant led to a lower conversion rate of sulphide and a lower level of over-oxidation to sulfone. The oxidation of sulphide was found to be incomplete, but almost completely selective to sulfoxide when substoichiometric quantities of oxidant were used. Therefore, in order to obtain complete oxidation to sulfone, it would appear that the optimal substrate to oxidant ratio is 1:3. Conversely, a substrate to oxidant ratio of 1:1 should be appropriate to obtain sulfoxide as the major product.

Table 1 Molybdenum-catalysed oxidation of diphenylsulphide under different reaction conditions^a

Entry	Catalyst	Solvent	Oxidant	[S]/[O] ratio	T (°C)	t (h)	Conversion (%)	Selectivity to sulfoxide	Selectivity to sulfone
1	[Mo(O)(O ₂) ₂ (H ₂ O) _n]	H ₂ O	H ₂ O ₂	1:3	20	18	25	86	14
2	[Mo(O)(O ₂) ₂ (H ₂ O) _n]	Cl ₃ CH	H ₂ O ₂	1:3	20	18	6	100	0
3	[Mo(O)(O ₂) ₂ (H ₂ O) _n]	DMSO	H ₂ O ₂	1:3	20	18	10	100	0
4	[Mo(O)(O ₂) ₂ (H ₂ O) _n]	[C ₄ mim][PF ₆]	H ₂ O ₂	1:3	20	18	100	0	100
5	[Mo(O)(O ₂) ₂ (H ₂ O) _n]	[C ₄ mim][PF ₆]	H ₂ O ₂	1:3	20	1	100	0	100
6	[Mo(O)(O ₂) ₂ (H ₂ O) _n]	[C ₄ mim][PF ₆]	H ₂ O ₂	1:3	0	1	90	65	35
7	[Mo(O)(O ₂) ₂ (H ₂ O) _n]	[C ₄ mim][BF ₄]	H ₂ O ₂	1:3	20	1	98	0	100
8	[Mo(O)(O ₂) ₂ (H ₂ O) _n]	[C ₈ mim][PF ₆]	H ₂ O ₂	1:3	20	1	97	0	100
9	[Mo(O)(O ₂) ₂ (H ₂ O) _n]	[C ₄ mim][NTf ₂]	H ₂ O ₂	1:3	20	1	100	0	100
10	-	[C ₄ mim][PF ₆]	H ₂ O ₂	1:3	20	1	0	0	0
11	[Mo(O)(O ₂) ₂ (H ₂ O) _n]	[C ₄ mim][PF ₆]	TBHP	1:3	20	1	72	100	0
12	[Mo(O)(O ₂) ₂ (H ₂ O) _n]	[C ₄ mim][PF ₆]	LiClO ₄	1:3	20	18	0	0	0
13	[Mo(O)(O ₂) ₂ (Mepz) ₂]	[C ₄ mim][PF ₆]	H ₂ O ₂	1:3	20	1	100	0	100
14 ^b	[Mo(O)(O ₂) ₂ (H ₂ O) _n]	[C ₄ mim][PF ₆]	H ₂ O ₂	1:3	20	1	85	59	41
15 ^b	[Mo(O)(O ₂) ₂ (Mepz) ₂]	[C ₄ mim][PF ₆]	H ₂ O ₂	1:3	20	1	84	81	19

^a Reaction conditions: catalyst 0.025 mmol, diphenylsulphide 1.0 mmol, solvent 2.0 mL, oxidant 3 mmol. After extraction with Et₂O (4 x 5 mL), the yields and selectivity were calculated by GC (50 µl of dodecane as internal standard). (Abbreviations: DMSO = dimethylsulfoxide, TBHP = *tert*-butyl hydroperoxide, Mepz = 3-methylpyrazole). ^b Catalyst 0.0025 mmol.

Fig. 1 Molybdenum-catalysed oxidation of diphenylsulfide in $[C_4mim][PF_6]$ at different substrate:oxidant ratios (see text for reaction conditions).

Selective oxidation of sulphides to sulfones

The optimised reaction for the oxidation of sulphide to sulfone was carried out using $[Mo(O)(O_2)_2(H_2O)_n]$ as catalyst, with a 1:3:0.025 ratio of [sulphide:H₂O₂:catalyst] in the ionic liquid $[C_4mim][PF_6]$ at 20 °C. To generalise the developed procedure, different sulphides with different functional groups were tested. The reaction time was fixed at 18 h in order to ensure that the reaction went to completion for all the substrates. The results obtained in this study are shown in Table 2.

As stated before, and was regularly observed in catalytic sulphide oxidation studies, alkyl-substituted sulphides are more electron-rich substrates and therefore more easily oxidised than aryl-substituted sulphides. Therefore, as expected, alkylaryl-substituted sulphides (entries 1-5, Table 2) and dialkylsulphides such as tetrahydrothiophene (entry 6, Table 2) afforded complete oxidation to the corresponding sulfone product. The electronic nature of the substituent in the *para* position of the phenyl group of sulphides derived from thioanisole (entries 2-4) seems to have no effect on the conversion to sulfone under these reaction conditions.

Table 2 Oxidation of several sulphides (R^1R^2S) to sulfones in $[C_4mim][PF_6]$ using $[Mo(O)(O_2)_2(H_2O)_n]$ as catalyst^a

Entry	R^1	R^2	Conversion (%)	Selectivity to sulfone (%)
1	Ph	Me	100	100
2	<i>p</i> -Me- C_6H_4	Me	100	100
3	<i>p</i> -Cl- C_6H_4	Me	100	100
4	<i>p</i> -Br- C_6H_4	Me	100	100
5	Ph	Et	100	100
6	Tetrahydrothiophene		100	100
7	Dibenzothiophene		100	100
8	Benzothiophene ^b		67	100
9	Thiophene		0	0

^a Reaction conditions: aqueous $[Mo(O)(O_2)_2(H_2O)_n]$ 0.025 mmol, substrate 1.0 mmol, $[C_4mim][PF_6]$ 2.0 mL, 30 % aqueous hydrogen peroxide 3 mmol. T = 20 °C, t = 18 h. After extraction with Et_2O (4 x 5 mL), the yields and selectivity were calculated by GC (50 μ l of dodecane as internal standard). ^b Complete conversion at 60 °C.

The catalytic system was also suitable for oxidising thiophene derivatives. The removal of sulphur-containing compounds is of great interest due to its presence in diesel fuel. Oxidation of thiophene derivatives such as dibenzothiophene (DBT) and benzothiophene (BT) in fuels, followed by extraction of the sulfone products proved to be one of the better available methods for sulphur removal.^{7,12c} In this respect, several research teams have focused on sulphide oxidation in ionic liquids. The ionic liquids selected were used both as reaction media and as extractants, which dissolve the formed sulfones.^{7a-c,15a} Interestingly, Li and co-workers have reported a simple liquid-liquid extraction and catalytic oxidative desulphurisation system composed of molybdic compound, such as $Na_2MoO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$, $(NH_4)_6Mo_7O_{24} \cdot 4H_2O$, 30% H_2O_2 , and 1-butyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate ($[C_4mim][BF_4]$) for the deep removal of DBT in model oil.^{12c} The present procedure allows a relatively easy catalytic oxidation of DBT to sulfone with quantitative yields under mild conditions (entry 7, Table 2). In agreement with others,³² BT was found to be more resistant to oxidation with hydrogen peroxide than DBT, and incomplete oxidation to sulfone was observed in the developed procedure (entry 8, Table 2). However, by conducting the reaction at higher temperature (60 °C), this oxidation was controlled and sulfone function was again obtained selectively. Finally, thiophene showed no evidence of oxidation (entry 9, Table 2) as a consequence of its aromaticity.

Selective oxidation of sulphides to sulfoxides

The selective oxidation of sulphides to sulfoxides is an attractive and important method in organic chemistry, since sulfoxides are important intermediates of biological molecules,² chiral auxiliaries³ and oxo-transfer reagents.⁴ When considering the methods of sulfoxide synthesis, oxidation of sulphides is the most straightforward one. There are a lot of reagents available for the sulfoxidation reaction; however, most of them are not satisfactory because of the formation of environmentally-unfavourable by-products and low oxygen atom efficiency. Moreover, overoxidation of the sulfoxides to their sulfones is a common problem during the oxidation of sulphides. Therefore, the conditions of the reaction (*i.e.* time, temperature, and sulphide to oxidant ratio) have to be controlled to avoid forming side products of the reaction. In agreement with the conclusion obtained from the studies described above on the influence of the solvent, oxidant, substrate/oxidant ratio and catalyst, the optimised reaction for the oxidation of sulphide to sulfoxide was carried out using $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{Mepz})_2]$ as catalyst, with a 1:1:0.025 ratio of [sulphide substrate:H₂O₂:catalyst] in the ionic liquid $[\text{C}_4\text{mim}][\text{PF}_6]$ maintained at 20 °C for 1 h. To generalise the developed procedure, different sulphides with different functional groups were analysed. The results obtained in this study are shown in Table 3, where the results obtained using the catalyst $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n]$ are also included for comparison. Good catalytic activity and selectivity were obtained for alkyl/aryl-substituted sulphides (entries 1-7, Table 3). In all cases, the selectivity to sulfoxide is better with the catalyst $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{Mepz})_2]$ than with $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n]$. For the latter, unwanted sulfone was always identified as a minor product. As expected, oxidation of alkyl/aryl-substituted sulphides (entries 2-5, Table 3) or dialkyl sulphides such as tetrahydrothiophene (entry 7, Table 3) was slightly better than the oxidation of diphenylsulphide (entry 1). The electronic nature of the substituent in the *para* position of the phenyl-ring substituted sulphides seems to have no significant effect on the conversion to sulfoxide under these reaction conditions. Finally, in reactions with BT and DBT, the oxidation gave unwanted sulfone almost as the sole product of the reaction and, consequently, very low values of selectivity to sulfoxide. This result was not unexpected since thiophene derivatives are much less reactive than their corresponding sulfoxides, as a consequence of its aromaticity.

Table 3 Oxidation of several sulphides (R¹R²S) to sulfoxides in [C₄mim][PF₆].^a

Entry	R ¹	R ²	Catalyst [Mo(O)(O ₂) ₂ (Mepz) ₂]		Catalyst [Mo(O)(O ₂) ₂ (H ₂ O) _n]	
			Conversion (%)	Selectivity to sulfoxide (%)	Conversion (%)	Selectivity to sulfoxide (%)
1	Ph	Ph	79	83	90	74
2	Ph	Me	80	96	83	89
3	<i>p</i> -Me-C ₆ H ₄	Me	87	85	91	66
4	<i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄	Me	91	87	92	86
5	<i>p</i> -Br-C ₆ H ₄	Me	88	83	89	75
6	Ph	Et	92	73	93	67
7	Tetrahydrothiophene		95	79	93	55
8	Dibenzothiophene		63	3	67	1
9	Benzothiophene		65	1	16	10

^a Reaction conditions: Mo catalyst 0.025 mmol, sulphide substrate 1.0 mmol, [C₄mim][PF₆] 2.0 mL, 30 % aqueous hydrogen peroxide 1 mmol. T = 20 °C, t = 1 h. After extraction with Et₂O (4 x 5 mL), the conversion and the selectivity were calculated by GC (50 µl of dodecane as internal standard).

Catalyst recycling

One of the main reasons for using ionic liquids as reaction media was to study the possibility of recycling and reusing them along with the dissolved molybdenum catalyst. This is a well-known advantage for many catalysed reactions in ionic liquids, with reported precedents.^{17, 28b} As such, recycling the catalyst/[C₄mim][PF₆] mixture after product extraction was then investigated.

Recycling experiments were performed for the sulfoxidation of diphenylsulphide using [Mo(O)(O)₂(H₂O)_n] as catalyst. In a previous work, we demonstrated that recycling the [Mo(O)(O)₂(dmpz)₂]/IL mixture is possible.^{28b} However, the 3,5-dimethylpyrazole ligand was slowly removed during the product extraction, and thus a steady decline was observed in the catalytic activity throughout the recycling experiments. In order to compensate for the partial ligand extraction produced during the epoxide extraction, 3,5-dimethylpyrazole was also added along with the reactants.^{28b} For this reason, we decided to use [Mo(O)(O)₂(H₂O)_n] as catalyst in the sulfoxidation recycling experiments, instead of [Mo(O)(O)₂(Mepz)₂], in order to prevent ligand leaching. For other details please refer to the Experimental section. Interestingly, the recycled catalyst could be used for at least ten reaction cycles without a significant change in conversion or selectivity. The results, shown in Fig. 2, clearly confirmed the practical reusability of the catalyst, under the described reaction conditions.

Stoichiometric reaction between molybdenum complex and diphenylsulphide

Mechanistic aspects involving oxodiperoxomolybdenum complexes as catalyst in oxidation reactions are well established.²³ These suggest the formation of a dioxoperoxomolybdenum complex after the oxygen transfer step.²⁸ It is also well established that the resulting monoperoxo complex always shows lower activity for oxygen transfer to substrate than the diperoxo complex with the same ligands.³³ For instance, in a previous study on stoichiometric epoxidation of olefins by oxodiperoxomolybdenum complexes, we demonstrated that complexes are capable of oxidising just one equivalent of olefin, strongly indicating that direct oxygen transfer to olefin exhibits higher barriers for monoperoxo complexes than their diperoxo counterparts.^{28a,33} Although stoichiometric reactions between sulphides and oxodiperoxomolybdenum complexes have already been described,^{13f,34} we decided to investigate the stoichiometric reaction between the complex [Mo(O)(O)₂(Mepz)₂] and diphenylsulphide in the ionic liquid [C₄mim][PF₆], in order to extend the studies of the

Fig. 2 Conversion and selectivity to diphenylsulfoxide (%) for ten catalytic cycles of the Mo-catalysed oxidation of diphenylsulphide with hydrogen peroxide in $[C_4min][PF_6]$ as solvent (for reaction conditions see Table 3).

Mo-catalysed oxidation of sulphides and gain information about the reaction mechanism. The molybdenum complex was reacted with the sulphide in a 1:1 ratio (Mo:sulphide) in the absence of an additional oxidant. The reaction conditions were the same as those optimised in the catalytic studies (*vide supra*) and are described in the Experimental section. The oxodiperoxomolybdenum complex was shown to oxidise the diphenylsulphide almost completely and, accordingly, the major product was diphenylsulfone, despite the absence of oxidant. This result strongly confirms that the complex is capable of transferring two oxygen atoms, from the two coordinated peroxy ligands to the substrate, affording a dioxoperoxomolybdenum intermediate and, probably, a trioxomolybdenum(VI) species (Scheme 2). In a related study, Cass et al. observed that aliphatic and aromatic sulphides were oxidised to sulfoxides using oxodiperoxomolybdenum complexes coated on silica gel in a 1:1 ratio (Mo:sulphide); however, sulfones were the main products of the reaction when the complexes were not coated on silica gel.^{13f} These observations fit well with a reaction mechanism in which direct oxygen transfer to sulphur compound (sulphide or sulfoxide) exhibits comparable barriers for the oxodiperoxomolybdenum complex as their monoperoxy counterpart. This fact has been confirmed by the DFT studies discussed below.

Scheme 2

Direct evidence of the formation of $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})_2(\text{O}_2)(\text{Mepz})]$ or $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})_3(\text{Mepz})]$ complexes were not experimentally observed under catalytic conditions. However, both dioxoperoxomolybdenum(VI)^{28a} and trioxomolybdenum(VI)³⁵ type compounds have been described in the bibliography. In order to attempt to isolate the dioxoperoxo intermediate, the stoichiometric reaction of dimethylsulfoxide and the complexes $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{L})_2]$ ($\text{L} = \text{Mepz}$, dmpz , pz) were carried out in water, at preparative scale, without added oxidant. In these reactions, the complexes $[\text{HMepz}]_4[\text{Mo}_8\text{O}_{26}(\text{Mepz})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, **1**, $[\text{Hdmpz}]_4[\text{Mo}_8\text{O}_{26}(\text{dmpz})_2] \cdot 2\text{dmpz}$, **2**, and $[\text{Hpz}]_4[\text{Mo}_8\text{O}_{22}(\text{O}_2)_4(\text{pz})_2] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, **3**, were obtained and structurally characterised (see below). Their formation was easily rationalised on the basis of the formation of the aforementioned dioxoperoxo- and trioxo- compounds and the ability of oxomolybdenum species to oligomerise in water solution,³⁶ according to equations shown in Scheme 3.

Scheme 3

X-ray studies: structural characterization of several octamolybdate complexes

From the stoichiometric reactions, discussed above, well-formed crystals of the compounds $[\text{HMepz}]_4[\text{Mo}_8\text{O}_{26}(\text{Mepz})_2]\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, **1**, $[\text{Hdmpz}]_4[\text{Mo}_8\text{O}_{26}(\text{dmpz})_2]\cdot 2\text{dmpz}$, **2**, and $[\text{Hpz}]_4[\text{Mo}_8\text{O}_{22}(\text{O}_2)_4(\text{pz})_2]\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, **3**, were obtained and characterised by X-ray diffraction methods. Although in the preparation of **1** the employed reagent is 3-methylpyrazole, the Mo-coordinated methylpyrazole found in the structure is the less sterically demanded 5-methylpyrazole isomer. This situation has been previously detected in other solid state systems³⁷ and it is due to the fast exchange equilibrium between the two tautomeric forms, eventually favouring the less sterically demanding 5-position in the complex.³⁸

All the compounds of Figs. 3-5 are characterized by an anionic octanuclear skeleton with four protonated pyrazoles as counterions. Selected geometric parameters are collected in ESI (Tables S5-S8). Given the interest for polyoxometalate chemistry,³⁹ the number of structurally-characterised octamolybdate compounds is high. Numerous cases of the anionic species $[\text{Mo}_8\text{O}_{26}(\text{L})_2]^{4-}$ are known⁴⁰ and, in particular for $\text{L} = \text{pyrazole}$, two crystalline phases of $[\text{Hpz}]_4[\text{Mo}_8\text{O}_{26}(\text{pz})_2]$ complex have been reported as γ -octamolybdate with different solvate molecules (refcodes JOWRAO and MEJWUT).⁴¹ The complexes $[\text{HMepz}]_4[\text{Mo}_8\text{O}_{26}(\text{Mepz})_2]\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, **1**, (Fig. 3) and $[\text{Hdmpz}]_4[\text{Mo}_8\text{O}_{26}(\text{dmpz})_2]\cdot 2\text{dmpz}$, **2**, (Fig. 4) are isostructural to these pyrazole derivatives. The fourteen terminal $\text{O}=\text{Mo}$ distances in each compounds are in the range 1.65-1.72 Å and compare well with those found in JOWRAO and MEJWUT (1.69-1.72 Å), and this also applies to the Mo-O lengths in the oxo-bridges. The Mo-N distances of 2.216(4) and 2.23(2) Å for **1** and **2**, respectively, are instead slightly shorter than the analogous Mo-pyrazole linkages (2.243(4) and 2.262(3) Å). The crystal packing in both compounds is characterised by hydrogen bonding interactions. For instance, two of the methylpyrazolium cations in **1** are involved in strong hydrogen bonds with the water molecules of solvation ($\text{N}-\text{H}\cdots\text{O}$, 2.657(5) and 2.697(5) Å), and these are also engaged by hydrogen bonding with oxo ligands ($\text{O}-\text{H}\cdots\text{O}$ range, 2.80-2.97 Å). The other two 3-methylpyrazolium cations form hydrogen bonds exclusively with the oxygen atoms of the octamolybdate anion ($\text{N}-\text{H}\cdots\text{O}$ range, 2.70-2.84 Å). The hydrogen bonding network is completed by intramolecular $\text{N}-\text{H}\cdots\text{O}$ interactions between the coordinated methylpyrazole and a terminal oxo ligand ($\text{N}-\text{H}\cdots\text{O}$, 2.790(5) and 2.820(5) Å).

Fig. 3 Structure of the anion of complex $[\text{Hmepz}]_4[\text{Mo}_8\text{O}_{26}(\text{Mepz})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, **1**. C-bound hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity. Selected bond distances (Å): Mo1-O2, 1.693(3); Mo1-O1, 1.702(3); Mo2-O5, 1.698(3); Mo2-O6 1.714(3); Mo3-O9 1.698(3); Mo4-O13 1.699(3); Mo4-O14 1.723(3); Mo5-O17 1.719(3); Mo5-O18 1.701(3); Mo6-O20 1.681(3); Mo7-O22 1.700(3); Mo7-O23 1.719(3); Mo8-O25 1.704(3); Mo8-O26 1.686(3); Mo4-N1, 2.216(4); Mo5-N3, 2.209(4).

Fig. 4 Structure of the anion of complex $[\text{Hdmpz}]_4[\text{Mo}_8\text{O}_{26}(\text{dmpz})_2] \cdot 2\text{dmpz}$, **2**. C-bound hydrogen atoms are omitted for clarity. Selected bond distances (Å): Mo1-O1, 1.708(17); Mo1-O2, 1.654(17); Mo2-O3, 1.983(17); Mo2-O4, 2.235(15); Mo2-O6, 1.658(17); Mo2-O7, 1.707(16); Mo3-O10, 1.711(15); Mo4-O12, 1.690(16); Mo4-O13, 1.724(16); Mo1-N1, 2.23(2).

The compound $[\text{Hpz}]_4[\text{Mo}_8\text{O}_{22}(\text{O}_2)_4(\text{pz})_2] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, **3**, (Fig. 5) represents a new example of the few structurally characterised peroxyoctamolybdate species.^{42,43} The compound is isomorphous to $[\text{Hdmpz}]_4[\text{Mo}_8\text{O}_{22}(\text{O}_2)_4(\text{dmpz})_2] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, previously reported by us,⁴³ and

features a distorted octahedral environment for the eight Mo centres. Overall, the centrosymmetric anion features ten terminal O=Mo moieties (1.68-1.70 Å range) and twelve non-equivalent bridging oxo groups. The corresponding Mo-O distances cover the large 1.77-2.44 Å range in view of their different κ^2 -, κ^3 - and κ^4 -coordination modes. Two Mo atoms are coordinated by a pyrazole ligand (Mo-N, 2.209(4) and 2.216(4) Å) and a peroxo one (O-O = 1.099(9) Å). Additionally, two other Mo atoms are coordinated by a second peroxo ligand with a much longer O-O distance of 1.317(7) Å. The crystal packing is also characterized by hydrogen bonding interactions, the pyrazolium cations strongly interacting with the oxo terminal ligands and/or solvated water molecules (N-H \cdots O range, 2.62 - 2.73 Å). The latter are also engaged in hydrogen bonding with the oxo ligands (O-H \cdots O range, 2.76 - 3.14 Å).

Fig. 5 Structure of the anion of complex [Hpz]₄[Mo₈O₂₂(O₂)₄(pz)₂] \cdot 3H₂O, **3**. Selected bond distances (Å): Mo1-O3, 1.699(4); Mo2-O7, 1.689(3); Mo3-O10, 1.700(4); Mo4-O13, 1.695(4); Mo1-N1, 2.220(4); O1-O2, 1.099(9); O14-O15, 1.317(7).

In an attempt of preparing the compound [Mo(O)(O₂)₂(im)₂] (im = imidazole), a small crop of well-formed yellow crystals was obtained. Their X-ray characterization identified as the compound [Him]₄[Mo₈O₂₄(O₂)₂(im)₂] \cdot 3H₂O, **4**. In spite of the accidental isolation, the crystal structure is presented here (Fig. 6, with selected geometric parameters in ESI) in view of its close similarity with the previous series of octanuclear compounds. Again, the octanuclear anion consists of distorted octahedral metals and is centrosymmetric. Twelve terminal O=Mo moieties are observed (1.68–1.74 Å range) as well as twelve bridging oxo groups (with κ^2 -, κ^3 - and κ^4 -coordination modes, hence in the large range of Mo–O distance (1.90–2.30 Å). At variance with the structure of **3**, there are two rather than four coordinated

peroxo ligands (O–O length of 1.287(6) Å) and two imidazole ones (Mo–N, 2.189(3) Å). A related known structure is that of $[\text{Him}]_4[\text{Mo}_8\text{O}_{26}(\text{im})_2]$ complex⁴⁴ conceptually derived upon the formal substitution of the two peroxo ligands with two oxo groups. In the crystals of **4**, there are four protonated imidazole counterions and three water crystallization molecules, which participate in a hydrogen bonding interactions comparable with those described above.

Fig. 6 Structure of the anion of complex $[\text{Him}]_4[\text{Mo}_8\text{O}_{24}(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{im})_2] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, **4**. Selected bond distances (Å): Mo1–O1, 1.735(3); Mo1–O2, 1.709(3); Mo2–O5, 1.689(2); Mo3–O11, 1.696(2); Mo4–O13, 1.717(2); Mo1–N1, 2.189(3); O9–O10, 1.287(6).

DFT study of the oxodiperoxomolybdenum-catalysed sulphide and sulfoxide oxidation mechanisms

Oxidoperoxocomplexes of molybdenum(VI) behave as electrophilic oxidants toward sulphides and sulfoxides,⁴⁵ according to the thianthrene 5-oxide probe.⁴⁶ Kinetic studies indicated that the sulphide or sulfoxide molecule does not coordinate to the molybdenum center.^{45c} Therefore, the oxidation process most likely follows a Sharpless-type outer-sphere concerted mechanism.⁴⁷ The oxygen atom transfer is produced by the nucleophilic attack of sulphide onto the peroxide ligand that cleavages the O–O bond with sulfoxide formation and the reduction of the peroxide into an oxo ligand. Pathways of this type have been explored from the theoretical point of view.²⁴

Our DFT study concerns the Sharpless-type catalytic cycle of Fig. 7, based on the experimental evidence that sulphides are catalytically oxidized by hydrogen peroxide in the

presence of oxodiperoxomolybdenum complexes $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{L})_2]$ ($\text{L} = \text{Mepz}$, **a**; dmpz , **b**; and H_2O , **c**). In these complexes, the L ligand *trans* to the oxo group is labile and, in fact, the release of one pyrazole ligand to give the catalytic active species $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{L})]$, **1a-c**, is exergonic (computed values of -1.5 and -5.5 $\text{kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ for $\text{L} = \text{Mepz}$, **a**, and dmpz , **b**, respectively).⁴³ The Mo-coordinated methylpyrazole ligand employed in the calculations corresponds to the less sterically hindered 5-methylpyrazole (see comments above^{37,38}). The overall ΔG reaction profile of the cycle for the Me_2S molecule and the compound **a** as the active $16e^-$ catalyst is shown in Fig. 8, while the optimized key intermediates and transition states structures appear in Fig. 9. Incidentally, only gas phase calculations were attempted, with the zero energy in Fig. 8 corresponding to the sum of the separate reactants $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{Mepz})] + \text{H}_2\text{O}_2 + \text{Me}_2\text{S}$. In this respect, it has been pointed out for other authors in related Mo-catalysed olefin epoxidations that the inclusion of solvent effects does not largely alters energy profiles.^{27c,48} The same occurred for sulfoxidation and in previous studies the differences between the gas-phase and solvent ΔG 's were no larger than $2\text{-}3$ $\text{kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ for several solvents.^{24a} Moreover, the absence of any ionic species along the pathway suggests that a PCM model may not be indispensable for this study.

The first step of the catalytic cycle concerns the oxygen atom transfer from a peroxide O atom in **1a** to the approaching dimethylsulphide through the transition state **TS(1a-2a)**. The possibility that Me_2S enters as a ligand in the vacant position of **1a** to afford the adduct $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{Mepz})(\text{Me}_2\text{S})]$ (not reported) can be discarded because the enthalpic contribution is insufficient to compensate the unfavourable entropic one. Such a system, with a Mo-S distance of 3.371 Å, lies $+8.8$ $\text{kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ higher with respect to the separated components. As previously noticed by some of us,⁴⁹ a functional which accounts for dispersion forces (*e.g.*, B97D⁵⁰) may provide more realistic description of possible weak bonding, but it was not tested in this case. In the transition state **TS(1a-2a)** the S-O distance is 2.253 Å, while the initial O-O linkage is already elongated from 1.446 value to 1.760 Å (additional structural parameters are given in the Fig. S1 of the ESI). The orbital analysis of the concerted Sharpless mechanism indicated that the oxo-transfer stems from the initial interaction between the HOMO of the sulphide substrate and the σ^* -(O-O) LUMO. The activation barrier at **TS(1a-2a)** of 23.3 $\text{kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ is slightly higher than those involving the analogous $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{OPH}_3)]$ ^{24b} and $[\text{CpMo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)(\text{Cl})]$ ²⁵ complexes (*ca.* 18 $\text{kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$), but it nicely compares with those computed for the interaction between peroxo titanium^{22a} or vanadium^{22c} complexes and MePhS (about 23 $\text{kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$). In this regard, we mention that a sulphide molecule similarly attacks a dihalogen one (*e.g.*, I-Br, isoelectronic with the peroxo

Fig. 7 Catalytic cycle theoretically investigated for the oxidation with hydrogen peroxide of sulphides MeRS (R = Me, Ph) to sulfoxides catalysed by $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{L})]$ complexes.

Fig. 8 Catalytic profile for the oxidation of dimethylsulphide to dimethylsulfoxide with hydrogen peroxide catalysed by $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{Mepz})]$, **1a**, following a Sharpless-type mechanism (relative ΔG in $\text{kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$).

Fig. 9 Structures of the intermediates and the transition states in the oxidation of dimethylsulphide to dimethylsulfoxide with hydrogen peroxide catalysed by $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{Mepz})]$, following a Sharpless-type mechanism.

O_2^{2-}) where the $\text{R}_2\text{S-I-Br}$ linear adduct is an actual minimum rather than a transition state, as validated by its solid state structure.⁵¹ Partial electron transfer from the S to the Br atom is already operative, even if full reduction to a bromide has not yet occurred. Thus, while the $\text{R}_2\text{S-I-Br}$ adduct may be stabilized, the corresponding **TS(1a-2a)** species promptly favours the oxygen abstraction by the sulphide as in the intermediate **2a**. Similar considerations on other inner redox mechanism through a linear triatomic moiety have been made by some of us.⁵² The similarity of the oxo ligands in **2a** are indicated by the almost equal $\text{Mo}=\text{O}$ distances of 1.727 and 1.745 Å. The dimethylsulfoxide product is weakly anchored to the metal (Mo-O distance of 2.26 Å) and, in fact, the separation of the ligand costs only 1.0 $\text{kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ to give the $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})_2(\text{O}_2)(\text{Mepz})]$ complex **3a**. This, or similar species, is normally proposed as intermediate in epoxidation mechanisms and was also experimentally corroborated by some of us through a solid state structural determination.^{28a,43} An interesting stereochemical aspect of **3a** concerns the quasi perpendicular orientation of the peroxo ligand with respect to the dioxo $\text{Mo}(\text{O})_2$ plane. In actuality, also the coplanar conformer (not reported) could be optimized but found to lie 29.1 $\text{kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ higher in energy and its instability is indicated by two imaginary frequencies. A qualitative MO analysis clearly shows significant electronic differences, in particular at the minimum **3a** the $\text{Mo}(\text{O}_2)$ moiety is stabilized by one

delocalized π bonding interaction (besides the σ ones), since an hybrid metal d_{π} orbital much better accepts the electrons of an $O_2 \pi^*$ level.

From **3a**, the initial oxodiperoxo compound **1a** can be again obtained through reaction with H_2O_2 , to restart the catalytic cycle. Since the evolution of this type was not analyzed in the work of Sensato *et al.*,²⁴ we monitored the possible steps, which compare with those of the epoxidation catalytic cycle, already investigated by some of us. Initially, H_2O_2 is activated in the species **4a**, through a combined interaction of one O atom of the oxidant with Mo (separation of 2.441 Å) and the non-linear hydrogen bonds formed by the corresponding O-H groups with one oxo and the peroxy ligand (the two $H\cdots O$ separations are 2.320 and 1.848 Å, respectively). The proton transfer is completed in the species **5a**, which associates together oxo, peroxy, hydroxy and hydroperoxy ligands. The energy gain with respect to **4a** + H_2O_2 is 3.8 kcal·mol⁻¹, while a barrier of 11.8 kcal·mol⁻¹ must be overcome at the transition state **TS(4a-5a)**, where the transferring H atom is about halfway between two O ones (1.223 and 1.233 Å distances). Similar transition states, characterized by the interaction of HOOR (R = H, CH₃) with the O=Mo moiety, were also detected in previous epoxidation studies.^{43,53} An analogous pathway of the H_2O_2 activation was also reported by Calhorda *et al.* for the complex [CpMo(O)(O₂)(Cl)], although with a higher barrier (21.8 kcal mol⁻¹).²⁵ Compound **5a** can then rearrange to the barely less stable isomer **6a** ($\Delta G = 1.6$ kcal·mol⁻¹) thanks to combined torsions of the OH and OOH ligands about their linkages to the metal centre. This favours the transfer of the second H atom of the starting H_2O_2 molecule to the same oxo ligand, which eventually becomes a very weakly coordinated water ligand (Mo-OH₂ = 2.790 Å in **7a**). A barrier of 8.0 kcal·mol⁻¹ has to be passed at the transition state **TS(6a-7a)**, which features two similar O \cdots H distances of 1.178 and 1.274 Å, while the external O atom of the hydroperoxide ligand is close to the metal (2.186 Å). Transition states of the type **TS(6a-7a)** were detected in related water^{22a} or alcohol^{25,53,54,55} extrusion processes. Finally, water dissociation from **7a**, which corresponds to the deepest minimum in the pathway of Fig. 8 (-34.9 kcal·mol⁻¹), regenerates the initial species **1a** with an energy cost of only 4.1 kcal·mol⁻¹.

To evaluate the influence of different L coligands in the catalytic cycle from [Mo(O)(O₂)₂(L)], the energy profile of Fig. 8 was also constructed for L = dmpz, **b**; and H_2O , **c** (Figs. S2 and S3 of the ESI). The systems are very similar and, essentially, the profiles for the Mepz and dmpz ligands practically overlap each other (compare Figs. 8 and S2). In the case of a water coligand (complex **1c**), it is shown in Fig. 10 that the **TS(1-2)** barrier for the

oxo-transfer to dimethylsulphide is only $18.4 \text{ kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$, about $5 \text{ kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ lower than for the other analogues **1a** and **1b**. Barriers of $\sim 18 \text{ kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ were also found starting from the catalysts $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{OPH}_3)]^{24\text{b}}$ and $[\text{CpMo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)(\text{Cl})]^{25}$. The larger basicity of the pyrazole-type ligands vs. water must increase the electron density at the transferring peroxy oxygen atom, hence determine a higher repulsion (the Mulliken charges are -0.35 in **1a-b** versus -0.33 in **1c**). It is worth recalling that the influence of N-base additives on the efficiency of the Mo-catalysed hydrolysis of epoxides was already investigated by some of us to find out that indeed a stronger N-base reduces the Lewis acidic character of the metal, hence the efficiency of the process.^{28b}

Fig. 10 Comparison of the barriers calculated for the oxo-transfer step from $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{L})]$ ($\text{L} = \text{Mepz}$, **a**; dmpz , **b**; and H_2O , **c**) to dimethylsulphide with formation of the dioxoperoxo intermediate $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})_2(\text{O}_2)(\text{L})]$, **3a-c**, and dimethylsulfoxide (relative ΔG in $\text{kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$).

To investigate how the nature of the sulphide may affect the process, the behaviour of the catalyst $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{Mepz})]$, **1a**, toward the MePhS oxidation in place of the Me_2S substrate was also examined. The results, reported in the ESI (Figs. S4 and S5), indicate a somewhat larger activation barrier for the initial oxo-transfer step (27.2 vs. $23.3 \text{ kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$). Intuitively, the electron-withdrawing properties of the phenyl substituents reduce the nucleophilicity of the sulphur lone pair, hence the strengths of its attack on the peroxide. Additionally, the Ph substituent can cause a steric hindrance effect against the sulphide approach to peroxy.

In a previous computational analysis,²⁴ the oxidation of dimethylsulfoxide to the corresponding sulfone Me_2SO_2 was addressed through two possible alternative pathways characterized by similar barriers. Thus, the generated sulfoxide was allowed to interact with either the starting oxodiperoxo complex of type **1a-c** or with the dioxoperoxo intermediate of type **3a-c**. Since evidence for the complete oxidation of sulphide into sulfone was experimentally detected by us in several cases (see Table 2), the corresponding computational analysis was also tackled. In particular, we tried to discern the preferred pathway under the catalytic conditions. Accordingly, Fig. 11 compares the steps for the reaction of $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})_2(\text{O}_2)(\text{Mepz})]$, **3a**, with either hydrogen peroxide leading to the hydroxo/hydroperoxo species **5a** or with the previously generated sulfoxide. In the latter case, the sulfone formation occurs together with that of the complex $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})_3(\text{L})]$, **9a**. Similar profiles were evaluated for the coligands dmpz, **b**, and H_2O , **c**, and are presented in Figs. S6 and S7 (see ESI).

Fig. 11 Evolution of the intermediate $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})_2(\text{O}_2)(\text{Mepz})]$, **3a**, under catalytic conditions: oxidation of **3a** with hydrogen peroxide *versus* oxidation of the dimethylsulfoxide substrate with **3a**.

Although the direct oxidation of the sulfoxide with **3a** corresponds to the more exergonic pathway (-40.6 *vs.* -2.2 $\text{kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$), a definitely higher barrier has to be passed (25.0 *vs.* 13.4 $\text{kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$). Since, under catalytic conditions, the catalyst: H_2O_2 ratio is 1:120, it appears that the mechanism of sulfone formation is rather similar to that of the sulphide to sulfoxide oxidation. A conclusion of this type was also reached by Calhorda *et al.* for the

[CpMo(O)₂(Cl)] system and the associated sulphide and sulfoxide oxidations with HOOR (R = H, CH₃).²⁵ In summary, the catalytic cycle of Fig. 7, initiated by the complex [Mo(O)(O₂)₂(L)], **1a-c**, may easily integrate the dimethylsulfone production, as shown in Fig. 12. The additional step with respect to the sulfoxide production (Fig. 7) involves the transition state **TS(1-8)** (its selected structural parameters are given in the ESI), which precedes the sulfone adduct **8**. The barrier exceeds that of **TS(1-2)** by no more than 2 kcal·mol⁻¹. The intermediate **8**, which features the weak coordination of the dimethylsulfone (Mo-S, 2.351 Å), is closely related with the intermediate sulfoxide adduct **2a**. Importantly, the sequence of two comparable oxidation steps is consistent with the easy overoxidation of sulphide to sulfone, as experimentally observed in presence of an excess of hydrogen peroxide (see Table 2). This point was also highlighted by Sensato²⁴ and Calhorda²⁵ in their respective computational analyses. The reaction profile for the entire catalytic cycle is displayed in Fig. 13, while similar profiles for L = dmpz, **b**, and H₂O, **c**, are given in the Figs. S8 and S9, respectively (see ESI).

Fig. 12 Catalytic cycle theoretically investigated for the oxidation of sulfoxides MeRSO (R = Me, Ph) to sulfones with hydrogen peroxide catalysed by [Mo(O)(O₂)₂(L)] (L = Mepz, **a**; dmpz, **b**; and H₂O, **c**).

Fig. 13 Catalytic profile for the oxidation of dimethylsulfoxide to dimethylsulfone with hydrogen peroxide catalysed by $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{Mepz})]$, **1a**, following a Sharpless-type mechanism (relative Gibbs free energy in $\text{kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$).

Fig. 14 Comparison of the barriers calculated for the oxo-transfer step from $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{L})]$ ($\text{L} = \text{Mepz}$, **a**; dmpz , **b**; and H_2O , **c**) to dimethylsulfoxide with formation of the dioxoperoxo intermediate $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})_2(\text{O}_2)(\text{L})]$, **3a-c**, and dimethylsulfone (relative ΔG in $\text{kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$).

Fig. 14 compares for the three L ligands the barriers for the second oxo-transfer process, which leads to the sulfone derivative. Again, the energies for the complexes with the ligands Mepz and dmpz are rather similar (24.1 and 24.5 $\text{kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$, respectively), while the barrier is lower for the $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ complex (19.6 $\text{kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$). As stated before, the water ligand determines a behaviour closer to that of the catalysts $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{OPH}_3)]$ (20.6

$\text{kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$)^{24b} and $[\text{CpMo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)(\text{Cl})]$ ($19.5 \text{ kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$).²⁵ For their higher barriers, the complexes with a pyrazole ligand may seem less favourable in catalysis, but with respect to $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]$ they better control the sulphide oxidation for their larger selectivity toward the sulfoxide substrate. In this respect, Table 3 clearly indicated the higher selectivity to the sulfoxide product of the $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{Mepz})_2]$ catalyst precursor with respect to the $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n]$ analogue and these experimental results are corroborated by the calculations.

Theoretical study of the viability of a Thiel-type mechanism

We recently investigated the pathways proposed by Sharpless⁴⁷ and Thiel⁵⁶ for the olefin epoxidation catalysed by oxodiperoxomolybdenum complexes and found comparable energy barriers.⁴³ In the present case, the Thiel mechanism implies that the hydrogen peroxide oxidant is first activated by $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{L})]$ and precedes the oxo-transfer to Me_2S . Such a catalytic cycle is outlined in Fig. 15 for $\text{L} = \text{dmpz}$, while Figs. 16 and 17 present the reaction profile and the associated structures, respectively. First, a H_2O_2 molecule is activated by **1b** and forms the adduct **10b** thanks to H-bonding with O atoms from two peroxide ligands ($\text{O}\cdots\text{H}\cdots\text{O}$ separations of 1.823 and 2.394 Å). Additionally, **10b** is stabilised by an interaction between the N–H bond of the dmpz ligand and the H_2O_2 oxygen atom, which lies nearer to the molybdenum centre (N–H \cdots O distance of 1.948 Å). Subsequently, one H_2O_2 hydrogen atom moves toward one peroxide ligand, as shown by the transition state **TS(10b-11b)** with a barrier of $22.0 \text{ kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$. In the latter structure, the transferring H atom lies closer to the peroxide oxygen atom ($\text{O}\cdots\text{H}$ separation of only 1.036 Å), at the same time as the oxygen atom shortens its separation from the Mo centre to 2.276 Å.

The H-transfer is complete in **11b**, which hence features two hydroperoxide ligands. One of the latter is then attacked by the sulphide molecule at the side of the coordinated O atom to form eventually the species **12b** characterized by a sulfoxide molecule. The optimization of the transition state **TS(11b-12b)** indicates a barrier of $24.9 \text{ kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ to be passed, after which the formation of **12b** is significantly exergonic ($-26.9 \text{ kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$). In the latter species, a double hydrogen bonding pattern is observed involving the same sulfoxide oxygen atom and the H atoms of both the hydroxide and hydroperoxide ligands. The latter interaction does not appear to be essential for the stabilization since the cost for the complete sulfoxide separation to give **13b** is only $1.6 \text{ kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$. Remarkably, the latter corresponds to the species **5b** in Fig. 7 or Fig. 12, indicating an evident relationship with the Sharpless

Fig. 15 Catalytic Thiel-type cycle theoretically investigated for the oxidation of Me₂S to sulfoxide with hydrogen peroxide catalysed by [Mo(O)(O₂)₂(dmpz)], **1b**.

Fig. 16 Catalytic profile for the oxidation of dimethylsulphide to dimethylsulfoxide with hydrogen peroxide catalysed by [Mo(O)(O₂)₂(dmpz)], **1b**, following a Thiel-type mechanism (relative Gibbs free energy in kcal·mol⁻¹).

mechanisms, especially for the pathway which leads to the initial catalyst **1b**. This involves a structural reorganization of **13b** into **14b** at the cost of 3.9 kcal·mol⁻¹. Then, the external H atom of the hydroperoxo group starts transferring to the hydroxo one to form a H₂O ligand in

7b after passing the transition state **TS(14b-7b)** with a barrier of 16.9 kcal·mol⁻¹. The latter structure confirms the incipient formation of the dihapto peroxy ligand from the hydroperoxy one since the Mo-O distance is already as short as 2.266 Å. Finally, the initial catalyst **1b** is restored from **7b** in a slightly endergonic manner (4.8 kcal·mol⁻¹) and the cycle is closed.

Fig. 17 Structures of the intermediates and transition states in the oxidation of dimethylsulphide to dimethylsulfoxide with hydrogen peroxide catalysed by [Mo(O)(O₂)₂(dmpz)], **1b**, following a Thiel-type mechanism.

In order to discern between the Sharpless or Thiel types of mechanism, we adopted a previously defined criterion^{55,57} and looked for the highest barrier encountered in the two energy profiles but also for the energy of the most immediate precursor. Indeed, the barrier for the oxo-transfer step is similarly high for the transition states **TS(1b-2b)** in Fig. S2 (ESI) and **TS(11b-12b)** in Fig. 16 (namely, 23.7 and 24.9 kcal·mol⁻¹, respectively). However, the access to **TS(11b-12b)** from **11b** requires at 32.9 kcal·mol⁻¹ (Thiel), while that to **TS(1b-2b)** from **1b** is only 23.7 kcal·mol⁻¹ (Sharpless). Also, the difference between the lowest and the highest intermediate species is appreciably higher for the Thiel vs. the Sharpless mechanism (43.6 kcal·mol⁻¹, between intermediates **11b** and **7b**, vs. 17.1 kcal·mol⁻¹, between intermediates **4b** and **7b**) and, although the former cannot be definitively discarded, there are good hints that the Sharpless mechanism is favoured.

Theoretical study of the stoichiometric sulphide oxidation with oxodiperoxomolybdenum complexes in the absence of oxidant

After the catalytic sulfoxidation analyses, the oxidation of sulphides by oxodiperoxomolybdenum complexes in the absence of H_2O_2 was computationally explored in order to corroborate the experimentally observed sulfone formation, when the ratio between diphenylsulphide and the $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{Mepz})_2]$ is the stoichiometric 1:1. Similar findings were previously reported for related oxodiperoxomolybdenum complexes.^{45b,c,58} Implicitly, two oxygen atoms are transferred from distinct Mo-bound peroxo ligands to the sulphur atom. The proposed steps for the complete oxidation of sulphide in the stoichiometric reaction are shown in Fig. 18.

As mentioned above, the L ligand *trans* to the oxo group in the $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{L})_2]$ complexes is labile,⁴³ and, hence, the metal complexes $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{L})]$, **1a-c**, were considered the reactant of choice for the stoichiometric reaction with the substrate Me_2S in the absence of external oxidant. By recalling that in the Sharpless mechanism the sulphide activation precedes the H_2O_2 one, the access to the intermediate **2a-c** is warranted through **TS(1-2)** (Fig. 18 and first part of Fig. 7). The easy sulfoxide departure from **2a-c** affords **3a-c**. After the formation of **3a-c**, the sulfone formation seems to imply the S lone pair of the sulfoxide that can linearly attack the other peroxide ligand, possibly through the transition state **TS'(3-9)** (structural details in the ESI), and, after the sulfone departure, the trioxo molybdenum complex **9** may be obtained, already addressed in Fig. 11. The overall energy profile is shown in Fig. 19 and, for L = Mepz, the final process is largely exergonic ($-60.5 \text{ kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$). The two oxo-transfer steps have the comparable barriers of 23.3 and 24.9 $\text{kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$, consistently with the experimental sulfone detection in the stoichiometric process. Similar profiles, computed for L = dmpz and H_2O , are collected in the Figs. S10 and S11 (see ESI).

The dioxoperoxomolybdenum(VI)^{28a,43} and trioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes,³⁵ well described in the literature, correspond to the species **3a-c** and **9a-c** of the present study. Experimentally, attempts to isolate the dioxoperoxo species from the in water reaction between dimethylsulfoxide and complexes $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{L})_2]$ (L = Mepz; dmpz; and pyrazol, pz) failed. In contrast, the octanuclear $[\text{HMepz}]_4[\text{Mo}_8\text{O}_{26}(\text{Mepz})_2]\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, **1**, $[\text{Hdmpz}]_4[\text{Mo}_8\text{O}_{26}(\text{dmpz})_2]\cdot 2\text{dmpz}$, **2**, and $[\text{Hpz}]_4[\text{Mo}_8\text{O}_{22}(\text{O}_2)_4(\text{pz})_2]\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, **3**, complexes were obtained. Indeed, it is known that oxomolybdenum(VI) compounds have a tendency toward oligomerization in aqueous solution,⁵⁹ hence the formation of dioxoperoxo- and

trioxo- intermediates may lead to the octanuclear derivatives, $[\text{Mo}_8\text{O}_{26}(\text{L})_2]^{4-}$ (octamolybdate) or $[\text{Mo}_8\text{O}_{22}(\text{O}_2)_4(\text{L})_2]^{4-}$ (tetraperoxo-octamolybdate) obtained by using different “Mo-complex:dimethylsulfoxide” ratios (see Scheme 3). In other words, the detected octanuclear compounds indirectly corroborate the proposed reactions mechanisms.

Fig. 18 Proposed pathway for the stoichiometric reaction of oxodiperoxomolybdenum complexes with sulphides in the absence of external oxidant.

Fig. 19 Reaction profile for the stoichiometric oxidation of dimethylsulphide with $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{Mepz})]$ (relative Gibbs free energy in $\text{kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$).

Conclusions

Oxidiperoxomolybdenum-catalysed sulphide oxidation employing aqueous hydrogen peroxide as the oxidant in ionic liquids may afford the sulfoxide or sulfone product through

an adequate tuning of the catalyst and reaction conditions. These findings represent a green approach to the sulphide oxidation process since hydrogen peroxide was used as a green oxidant, ionic liquid solvents were recyclable, and catalyst precursors were easily obtained from commercially and economically available MoO_3 . In fact, the immobilisation of the catalyst in the IL allowed for very efficient catalyst recycling, and after ten cycles no significant diminution of the diphenylsulfoxide yield was observed. A DFT investigation of the sulfoxidation mechanism using hydrogen peroxide and the catalysts $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{L})]$ ($\text{L} = \text{Mepz}$, **a**; dmpz , **b**; and H_2O , **c**) supported an outer-sphere concerted mechanism of the Sharpless type in which the oxygen atom transfer involves the attack of a sulphide lone pair over one peroxide ligand. The alternative possibility of a Thiel-type mechanism was also monitored and although it cannot be definitely discarded, there are computational hints that the Sharpless mechanism is more favourable. The $\text{S}=\text{O}$ formation in the derived sulfoxide is associated to the conversion of one peroxy ligand to the oxo form, with formation of dioxoperoxomolybdenum species. This conversion occurs without any involvement of the metal atom in the redox process, the Mo oxidation state remaining +VI (d^0 metal). In order to close the catalytic cycle, the oxo group is substituted by the peroxy ligand. The two processes of the catalytic cycle, involving one O atom transfer (sulfoxide or water formation), occur under energetically reasonable pathways. The highest barrier of $23.3 \text{ kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ (for Mepz , **a**) is found for the oxo-transfer step to sulphide. It is also found that the sulphur atom of the sulfoxide product is still able to perform a second nucleophilic attack (with subsequent oxidative transformation to sulfone) over one peroxy ligand. The mechanism has similar features to that of the first oxidation process to sulfoxide with a slightly higher barrier (*ca.* $2 \text{ kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$). The comparable energies for the two successive oxo-transfer are corroborated by the experimental formation of the sulfone product in the reactions carried out both with an excess of oxidant (catalytic) and in the absence of the H_2O_2 oxidant (stoichiometric). The magnitude of the barriers for the oxo-transfer may be modulated by the choice of the L coligand, the pyrazol-type one determining a *ca.* $5 \text{ kcal}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ higher value with the respect to the H_2O ligand. This is in agreement with the experimentally proved higher selectivity toward the sulfoxide product of the Mo-pyrazole catalysts. The proposed dioxoperoxomolybdenum and trioxomolybdenum(VI) intermediates in the theoretical mechanism were indirectly confirmed by reacting dimethylsulfoxide and the complexes $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{L})_2]$ ($\text{L} = \text{Mepz}$, dmpz , pz) in water, without added oxidant. In these reactions, the complexes $[\text{HMepz}]_4[\text{Mo}_8\text{O}_{26}(\text{Mepz})_2]\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, **1**, $[\text{Hdmpz}]_4[\text{Mo}_8\text{O}_{26}(\text{dmpz})_2]\cdot 2\text{dmpz}$, **2**, and $[\text{Hpz}]_4[\text{Mo}_8\text{O}_{22}(\text{O}_2)_4(\text{pz})_2]\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, **3**, were obtained and structurally characterised. Their

formation was easily rationalised on the basis of the formation of these aforementioned dioxoperoxo- and trioxo- compounds and the ability of oxomolybdenum species to oligomerise in water solution.

Experimental

General

Synthetic reactions were performed under aerobic conditions. Solvents were purified appropriately prior to use, using standard procedures. Chemicals were obtained from commercial sources and used as supplied. The ionic liquids $[C_4mim]X$ ($X = PF_6, BF_4, NTf$) and $[C_8mim][PF_6]^{60}$ and compounds $[Mo(O)(O_2)_2(H_2O)_n]^{27c}$ and $[Mo(O)(O_2)_2(L)_2]$ ($L = pz, Mepz, dmpz$)^{28,31,43} were prepared according to literature procedures. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Model 883 spectrophotometer (Nujol emulsion in NaCl or KBr plates or in pressed KBr pellets). NMR spectra were recorded using a Bruker AMX-300 spectrometer with $^{13}C\{^1H\}$ and 1H shifts referenced to the residual solvent signals. All data are reported in ppm downfield from $Si(CH_3)_4$. The gas chromatograms (GC) were obtained using a Varian Chromatogram CP-3800 with nitrogen as the carrier gas. The chromatogram used a Varian automatic injector, model CP-8410, flame ionisation detector (FID), and a Varian column, model CP-8741. Elemental analyses (C, H, N) were conducted by the Centro de Investigaciones, Tecnología e Innovación (CITIUS) of the University of Sevilla on an Elemental LECO CHNS 93 analyser.

General procedure for catalytic oxidation of sulphide to sulfone

The reactor (a 50 mL vial equipped with a Young valve and containing a stirrer flea) was charged with 0.5 M aqueous $[Mo(O)(O_2)_2(H_2O)_n]$ (50 μ L, 0.025 mmol), the solvent (2 mL), the oxidant (30 % aqueous H_2O_2 , 3 mmol) and the sulphide substrate (1 mmol), in the aforementioned order. The reactor was sealed and heated to the corresponding temperature (usually at 20 °C), maintaining constant stirring in a thermostated oil bath for the duration of the reaction. Upon completion the reactor was immediately cooled to 0 °C and the products extracted with diethyl ether (4 x 5 mL). The resulting solution was dried ($MgSO_4$) and analysed by GC (50 μ L of dodecane as internal standard).

General procedure for catalytic oxidation of sulphide to sulfoxide

The reactor (a 50 mL vial equipped with a Young valve and containing a stirrer flea) was charged with the molybdenum catalyst (0.025 mmol), [C₄mim][PF₆] (2 mL), the oxidant (30 % aqueous H₂O₂, 1 mmol) and the sulphide substrate (1 mmol), in the aforementioned order. The reactor was sealed and heated to the corresponding temperature, maintaining constant stirring in a thermostated oil bath for 1 h. The work-up and product analysis of the reaction was analogous to the one described above in the general procedure for oxidation to sulfone.

Catalyst recycling

Recycling experiments were performed for the sulfoxidation of diphenylsulphide using aqueous [Mo(O)(O)₂(H₂O)_n] as catalyst. Studies were run with 1 h cycles, which give incomplete conversion and permit clearer analysis of changes in catalytic efficiency. Up to the product extraction, the experimental procedure for each cycle was conducted as detailed above (molybdenum catalyst 0.025 mmol, [C₄mim][PF₆] 2 mL, 30 % aqueous H₂O₂ 1 mmol, diphenylsulphide 1 mmol, T = 20 °C). Extraction with diethyl ether (4 x 5 mL) was carried out after each cycle and yields calculated by GC. Afterwards the reactor was stirred at room temperature and vacuum was applied to remove any volatile residues remaining in the reaction mixture. The reactor was then cooled and 30 % aqueous hydrogen peroxide (1 mmol) and diphenylsulphide (1 mmol) were again charged to the reactor which was sealed before repeating the sulfoxidation reaction in the manner detailed above.

Procedure for stoichiometric sulphide oxidation in [C₄mim][PF₆]

The complex [Mo(O)(O)₂(Mepz)₂] (0.2 mmol) and [C₄mim][PF₆] (2 mL) were charged to the reactor and stirred for 10 minutes to assist dissolution. Diphenylsulphide (0.2 mmol) was then added. The reactor was sealed and heated to the corresponding temperature, maintaining constant stirring in a thermostated oil bath for 18 h. The work-up and product analysis of the reaction was analogous to those described above in the procedure for catalytic oxidation.

Syntheses

[HMepz]₄[Mo₈O₂₆(Mepz)₂]·2H₂O, 1. To a solution of [MoO(O)₂(Mepz)₂] (248.8 mg; 0.73 mmol) in water (20 ml) was added DMSO (209 μl, 2.93 mmol). The mixture, which had initially a very intense yellow colour, was stirred for 30 minutes at room temperature, disappearing progressively the colour. The solution was then left to slowly evaporate resulting, after 24h, in the formation of white crystals of [HMepz]₄[Mo₈O₂₆(Mepz)₂]·2H₂O, which were collected by filtration, washed with acetone and diethyl ether and dried in air (60 mg, 40 % yield). IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3521, 3419, 3138, 3101, 2952, 2923, 2854, 1614, 1586, 1563, 1498, 1462, 1377, 1300, 1280, 1224, 1107, 1065, 948, 940, 931, 911, 880, 858, 813, 689, 666, 643, 634, 602, 546, 516, 488, 422, 416. ¹H RMN (CD₃OD, 300Hz): δ 2.32 (s, 3H, CH₃), 6.13 (d, 1H, J = 2.1Hz, CH), 7.53 (d, 1H, J = 2.1Hz, CH). ¹³C{¹H} RMN (CD₃OD, 75.47 Hz): δ 11.5 (s, CH₃), 105.7 (s, CH), 134 (s, CH), 145.0 (s, CCH₃). Elemental analyses calculated for C₂₄H₄₄Mo₈N₁₂O₂₈: C, 16.80; H, 2.58; N, 9.79. Experimental: C, 16.67; H, 2.57; N, 9.37.

[Hdmpz]₄[Mo₈O₂₆(dmpz)₂]·2dmpz, 2. To a solution of [MoO(O)₂(dmpz)₂] (1.04 g; 2.83 mmol) in water (60 ml) was added DMSO (202 μl, 2.83 mmol). The mixture was stirred for 30 minutes at room temperature. The solution was then left to slowly evaporate resulting, after 24h, in the formation of yellow crystals of [Hdmpz]₄[Mo₈O₂₆(dmpz)₂]·2dmpz, which were collected by filtration, washed with acetone and diethyl ether and dried in air (384 mg, 55 % yield). IR (KBr, cm⁻¹): 3582, 3279, 3127, 2921, 2855, 2723, 2668, 2676, 1794, 1604, 1567, 1531, 1463, 1394, 1377, 1357, 1292, 1192, 1151, 1054, 1028, 1014, 941, 916, 899, 847, 811, 734, 666, 627, 587, 537, 477, 460. ¹H RMN (CD₃OD, 300Hz): δ 2.27 (s, 6H, 2xCH₃), 5.97 (s, 1H, CH). ¹³C{¹H} RMN (CD₃OD, 75.47 Hz): δ 11.6 (s, CH₃), 105.6 (s, CH), 146.1 (s, CCH₃). Elemental analyses calculated for C₄₀H₇₀Mo₈N₁₆O₂₆: C, 24.53; H, 3.60; N, 11.44. Experimental: C, 23.92; H, 3.52; N, 11.03.

[Hpz]₄[Mo₈O₂₂(O₂)₄(pz)₂]·3H₂O, 3. To a solution of [MoO(O)₂(pz)₂] (1.00 g; 3.22 mmol) in water (40 ml) was added DMSO (230 μl, 3.22 mmol). The mixture was stirred for 30 minutes at room temperature. The solution was then left to slowly evaporate resulting, after 24 h, in the formation of orange crystals of [Hpz]₄[Mo₈O₂₂(O₂)₄(pz)₂]·3H₂O, which were collected by filtration, washed with acetone and diethyl ether and dried in air (385 mg, 84 % yield). IR (KBr, nujol, cm⁻¹): 3582, 3542, 3413, 3272, 3120, 2923, 2854, 2676, 1579, 1517, 1464, 1405, 1377, 1355, 1268, 1164, 1129, 1068, 1055, 945, 900, 814, 783, 710, 666, 631, 602, 568, 547, 450. ¹H RMN (CD₃OD, 300Hz): δ 6.40 (br t, 1H, J = 2.1Hz, CH), 7.72 (br s,

2H, 2xCH). $^{13}\text{C}\{^1\text{H}\}$ RMN (CD_3OD , 75.47 Hz): δ 106.1 (s, CH), 134.9 (s, CH). Elemental analyses calculated for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{34}\text{Mo}_8\text{N}_{12}\text{O}_{33}$: C, 12.61; H, 2.00; N, 9.81. Experimental: C, 12.65; H, 1.98; N, 9.72.

[Him]₄[Mo₈O₂₄(O₂)₂(im)₂] \cdot 3H₂O, 4. To an aqueous 0.23 M solution of $[\text{Mo}(\text{O})(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_n]$ (15 ml, 3.45 mmol) was added imidazole (0.23 g, 3.45 mmol). The mixture was stirred for 30 minutes at room temperature and the solution was then left to slowly evaporate. In one of the reactions a small crop of well-formed yellow crystals were obtained, which were collected by filtration, washed with acetone and diethyl ether and dried in air (26 % yield). They were characterised by X-ray diffraction methods as the complex $[\text{Him}]_4[\text{Mo}_8\text{O}_{24}(\text{O}_2)_2(\text{im})_2]\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$. IR (NaCl, nujol, cm^{-1}): 1614, 1580, 1546, 1505, 1462, 1377, 1329, 1262, 1199, 1142, 1108, 1090, 1071, 1044, 956, 931, 888, 758, 720, 692, 654, 623. Elemental analyses calculated for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{34}\text{Mo}_8\text{N}_{12}\text{O}_{31}$: C, 12.85; H, 2.04; N, 9.99. Experimental: C, 12.44; H, 2.12; N, 10.42.

X-ray structural studies

A summary of the crystallographic data and structure refinement results for compounds **1-4** is given in Table S9 (ESI). The supplementary crystallographic data for these compounds are contained in the CCDC 1004213 - 1004216 refcodes, respectively. Data collections for these new compounds were performed on a Bruker-Nonius X8Apex II CCD diffractometer equipped with graphite-monochromated Mo-K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$). Intensity data were collected at 173(2) K. The data were reduced (SAINT)⁶¹ and corrected for absorption effects by the multi-scan method (SADABS).⁶² The structures were solved by direct methods (SIR-2002)⁶³ and refined against all F^2 data by full-matrix least-squares techniques (SHELXTL-6.12)⁶⁴ minimizing $w[F_o^2 - F_c^2]$. All non-hydrogen atoms were refined anisotropically. The hydrogen atoms were included from calculated positions and refined riding on their respective carbon atoms with isotropic displacement parameters, except the hydrogen atoms bonded to the nitrogen atoms in pyrazole rings and those bonded to an oxygen atom in water, which were detected from a difference Fourier map and refined isotropically with both N-H and O-H distances restrained to 0.90(2) \AA .

Computational details

The electronic structure and geometries of the model compounds were computed using density functional theory at the B3LYP level.⁶⁵ The Mo atom was described with the LANL2DZ basis set⁶⁶ while the 6-31G(d,p) basis set was used for the C, N, O, S and H atoms. The optimised geometries of all the compounds were characterised in the gas-phase as minima on the basis of their vibrational frequencies. In some case, a structure was considered a minimum in spite of a very low imaginary frequency ($< 20 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), possibly due to the usage of an insufficiently large integration grid.⁶⁷ Transition states were located using the quadratic synchronous transit (QST2) approach⁶⁸ and frequency calculations were performed in order to check the stationary states (NImag = 1). The energy profiles are presented in terms of free energies, derived from thermochemical analysis. The DFT calculations were performed using the Gaussian 03 suite of programs.⁶⁹ The cartesian coordinates and energetic parameters of all optimised compounds are reported in the SI.

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